

University-business cooperation on SMEs: An intervention program on creativity, critical thinking and trust

Ana Teresa Ferreira-Oliveira¹, Ana Bouças², Ana Rita Alves³

¹ CISAS, Escola Superior de Tecnologia e Gestão, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Rua Escola Industrial e Comercial de Nun'Alvares, 4900-347, Viana do Castelo, Portugal

² Escola Superior de Tecnologia e Gestão, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Rua Escola Industrial e Comercial de Nun'Alvares, 4900-347, Viana do Castelo, Portugal

³ Escola de Psicologia, Universidade do Minho, Braga, Portugal

Email: ateresaoliveira@estg.ipvvc.pt

Abstract

University-business cooperation is crucial on sustainable knowledge exchange and co-creation of knowledge. Regarding small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) the topic gains even more relevance. Academia has been developing relevant projects of cooperation with organizations but we have still a long way to go in diminishing the gap towards SMEs. This paper presents results from an intervention program developed by a professor and her students. It was implemented in 5 SMEs with 25 participants, ranged between 20 to 45 years. The intervention and training program had a total duration of 5 sessions with 50 minutes each. The program used a workshop "hands on" approach. An initial and final individual evaluation on creativity, trust and critical thinking was conducted through within-process and cross-process skills. The "hands on" was developed based on active learning, with the use of creativity dynamics, fostering critical thinking and trust dilemmas, developing cross-process skills. At the end of the program an individual report was delivered to each participant and feedback was sent individually in an incremental and developmental approach, associating each effective individual gains. This paper presents results from this intervention program integrating quantitative results, initial and final individual evaluations. Results show significant increases in all skills and creativity standing out as the most enhanced skill on the individual developmental process. The paper will also discuss future policies implications towards competence development on this area and the role of higher education institutions.

Keywords: active learning, creativity, critical thinking, trust, innovative experiences, competence development, training

1 Introduction

Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and academia are still working on establishing relevant university-business cooperation. Some efforts are being made on training modules but a stronger and cohesive work is relevant in order to enhance innovation and development (Ferreira-Oliveira & Bouças, 2020). This paper presents results from an intervention program developed by a professor and her students in SMEs with the purpose of fostering trust, creativity and critical thinking. It was implemented in 5 SMEs with 25 participants, between 20 to 45 years. The intervention and training program had a total duration of 5 sessions with 50 minutes each. The program used a workshop "hands on" approach and as major goals: a) to develop creativity and critical thinking skills in the participants; b) to promote knowledge about theories of thought and creative behavior, critical thinking theories; c) to understand the level of organizational trust experienced in the company; d) to promote hetero-knowledge; e) to develop students proficiency in these skills development.

2 Trust, critical thinking and creativity

2.1 Trust

Organizational trust has been highlighted as a relevant attitude in organizational processes and related to the development of individual skills in organizational settings (Ferreira-Oliveira & Bouças, 2020; Ferreira-Oliveira, Keating & Silva, 2018). There is a vast literature around the concept of organizational trust, characterized by several theoretical approaches, levels of analysis and empirical models (Mayer, Davis & Schoorman, 1995; Rousseau, Sitkin, Burt & Camerer, 1998; Spreitzer & Mishra, 1999; Dirks & Ferrin, 2001; Jr, Hansen & Pearson, 2004; Mollering, Bachmann & Lee, 2004; Keating, Silva & Veloso, 2010). It is important to clarify the trust

construct analysed in this work. A distinction that helps to clarify the concept is the nature of the trusted. When the target of trust is an individual, it refers to interpersonal trust, if the target is an organization, institutional trust arises (Lewicki & Bunker, 1996). In this work, we will use the interpersonal trust model, based on Mayer, Davis and Schoorman (1995). Rousseau, Sitkin, Burt and Camerer (1998, p. 395) define trust as “a psychological state comprising the intention to accept vulnerability based upon positive expectations of the intentions or behavior of another”. Organizational trust has a recognized influence on individual and organizational results such as increased performance (Costa, Roe & Taillieu, 2001; Gould-Williams, 2003), well-being of employees (Baptiste, 2008), job satisfaction (Driscoll, 1978; Perry & Mankin, 2007), team development (Costa et al., 2001) the development of a positive supervisor-employee relationship (Brower, Schoorman & Tan, 2000) and the employee-organization relationship (Kuvaas, 2008). Despite different models, there is a consensus in the literature regarding the conditions for the existence of interpersonal trust (Mach, Dolan & Tzafrir, 2010; Lehmann-Willenbrock, Grohmann & Kauffeld, 2012) the presence of vulnerability (Mayer & Davis, 1999) and the acceptance of risk (the substitution of control mechanisms by trust), the existence of mutual interactions between the parties and, finally, the expectations of consistent conduct over time. Organizational trust comprises an associated expectation that in work relationships where there is trust (namely between employee and manager) more effective collaboration coexists between members of an organization. The acceptance of risk in trust development, as in creativity, can be relevant to foster skills on a training program.

2.2 Critical Thinking

The Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and the European Commission revealed which are the indispensable competences for the exercise of full, active and creative citizenship in the XXI century (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019). Regarding the world of work and the advancement of society, is important to understand critical thinking as a key competence for success ((Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019; Lopes, Silva, Dominguez, Payan-Carreira, Catarino, Morais & Vasco, 2019). Furthermore, considering that we live in a time with greatest complexity and information overload it has never been more important to develop critical thinking skills, which allow us to distinguish facts from opinions, truths from lies, what is trivial of what is important, and thus making decisions about what to believe or what to do (Levitin, 2014). Ruggiero (2014) distinguished characteristics of the non-critical thinker and the critical thinker, in order to enhanced scientific understanding. The first one – non critical thinker - refers to those who accept the truth of things even if it is not supported by any kind of evidence; those who consider controversial problems and issues as threats to the ego and who tend to follow their feelings and impulses. On the other hand, the critical thinker recognizes what he does not know, his limitations and errors; is interested in the ideas of others, even though they tend to disagree with them and are contained, controlling their feelings and think before acting (Cruz, Dominguez & Payan-Carreira, 2019). In short, a non-critical thought happens quickly, effortlessly, unconsciously, automatically, associative, heuristic, non-reflective and implicit; while critical thinking is structured slowly, effortlessly, consciously, controlled, based on rules, analytical, reflective and explicit (Ruggiero, 2014). Critical thinking is also combined with the ability to distance oneself from the problem considering various alternatives and make quality judgments based on these alternatives. The act of thinking critically is seen as a cyclic and an interactive process where the evaluation of results and their impact can result in a review of the task, that is, in a new analysis and consequently new designs, implementations and evaluations. In this sense, critical thinking can be developed respecting four states: a) investigate: identify and question assumptions and ideas or generally accepted practices; b) imagine: consider various perspectives of a problem based on different premises; c) do: explain the strengths and limitations of a product, solution or theory justified by logical, ethical or aesthetic criteria; d) reflect on the solution or position chosen in comparison to its possible alternatives (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019). In addition, it is important to understand the individual skills and dispositions that lead an individual to think critically and that were addressed and developed in this investigation. With regard to competencies, the authors indicate six: a) interpretation: understanding and expressing the meaning and relevance of a variety of experiences, situations, judgments, beliefs, rules, procedures and criteria; b) analysis: identify the actual and intended inferential relationships between statements, questions, concepts, descriptions or other forms of representation designed to express beliefs, judgments, experiences, information or opinions; c) deduction: identify and guarantee the elements necessary to draw reasonable conclusions and consider information to reduce recurring consequences in the implementation; d) evaluation: assess the

credibility of extracts or other representations of beliefs, judgments, experiences, information or opinions; e) explanation: justify a decision based on conceptual and methodological considerations; f) self-regulation: conscious monitoring of cognitive activities and their results (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019). Regarding the internal dispositions necessary for the construction of a critical thinking, the authors named seven: a) search for the truth: openness to the search for the truth implies a greater receptivity for considering other facts and other perspectives; b) openness of mind: tolerance and understanding of divergent views and sensitivity to the possibility of one's own bias; c) analytical capacity: application of reasoning and use of evidence to solve problems, anticipating possible difficulties and being aware of the need to intervene; d) systematic thinking: being organized, orderly, focused and diligent; e) self-confidence: confidence in the solidity of their reasoned judgments and the ability to lead others in solving problems; f) curiosity: desire to learn, even when the application of knowledge is apparently not easy; g) cognitive maturity: making complex decisions involving several stakeholders, such as making ethical and policy-oriented decisions, particularly in environmental pressures (Vincent-Lancrin et al., 2019).

If, on the one hand, the study of the individual dimension of critical thinking is concerned with understanding the characteristics (competences and dispositions) that are behind what is or should be a critical thinker; the works of some authors interested in their interpersonal dimension seek to identify what a critical thinker does and what can become within a society. Cruz, Dominguez & Payan-Carreira (2019) says that educating for critical thinking ideally involves understanding education as a process of radical and transformative development, more than a mere process of cognitive development, enabling individuals to achieve their emancipation.

2.3 Creativity

In 1950, Guilford described divergent thinking, as the ability to originate a big number of noble ideas, and convergent thinking, the ability to choose ideas worth pursuing. Guilford described these two main processes integrated in creative thinking. Years later, Torrance (1970) added fluency, flexibility, originality and elaboration as aspects involved in the creativity processes. As Sternberg and Lubart (1999) put it "creativity is the ability to produce work that is both novel and appropriate". It can be found in all areas and creative people can be entrepreneurs, engineers, scientists and artists. With this diversity of domains, the best way to understand creativity is through the observed behaviours displayed by people labeled creative. These individuals usually look for ways to solve problems that others don't, are willing to take risks and stand up for their beliefs (Sternberg & Grigorenko, 2007). To explain the concept of creativity, more recently Lubart in 2017, created a conceptualizing framework of creativity, the 7 C's: creators, creating, collaborations, contexts, creations, consumption and curricula. Being creators are the ones that originate the creative content; creating the process and all the steps the creator takes to come up with their creations with or without collaboration from others or from any type of device. Lastly, consumption refers to the adoption of the creations, that can be either ideas or products and curricula are all the efforts made to the development of creativity within educational programs. Based on this conceptual basis, there is evidence to acknowledge that contrary to the common "myth" that creativity is a talent or a gift, it is a skill that can be gradually developed with the training of the cognitive processes involved in being creative (Sternberg & Lubart, 1995). This popular myth has limited the promotion and training of creativity in all types of contexts and within all types of people, hence, even though psychologist and other type of creativity researchers have been studying processes leading to creativity since the middle of the 20th century. Also, scarce intervention has been developed and only now creativity promotion interventions or training programs are being fostered. In 2019, Vincent-Lancrin et al (2019) proposed creativity rubrics to implement in creativity training programs: ability to inquire, imagine, do and reflect. It is noteworthy to mention that these dimensions are individual phenomena that need to be integrated within context characteristics in order to be fully comprehended. Thus, creativity can only be promoted if the efforts to develop the cognitive processes involved in being creative take into account the individual's social networks, domains and fields of performance (Ryhammar & Brolin, 1999). Following this idea, contexts affect the levels of individual creativity with the degree of which it facilitates the generation of new ideas; the amount of encouragement and support it gives to the development of creative ideas and products; and the judgment in the evaluation of the creative product (Sternberg & Lubart, 1999). Due the particular role of creativity in the innovative capacity and entrepreneurship of organizations, their efficiency to foster creative contexts is of utmost importance in these times of change (Aggarwal & Bhatia, 2011). Gomes, Rodrigues and Veloso (2016) summarized the

organizational dimensions that promote creative behaviours in their workers. These range from the physical characteristics of the workplace environment to aspects related to organizational culture and trust. To combine the development of internal and external dimensions to fully tackle the promotion of creativity in the workplace, corporations should enhance organizational dimensions, like support and encouragement from peers and leaders. In other hand, they should incorporate training programs for all staff with the purpose to develop competences that promote their creative potential and facilitate the innovation process (Stenberg, 2012; Gomes, Rodrigues & Veloso, 2016).

3 Method

This paper intends to present a project developed by a professor and her two master students who implemented the skills development program in 5 SMEs with 25 participants, between 20 to 45 years. The intervention and training program had a total duration of 5 sessions with 50 minutes each. The program used a workshop “hands on” approach. An initial and final individual evaluation on creativity, trust and critical thinking was conducted through within-process and cross-process skills. The “hands on” was developed based on active learning, with the use of creativity dynamics, fostering critical thinking and trust dilemmas, developing cross-process skills. At the end of the program an individual report was delivered to each participant and feedback was sent individually in an incremental and developmental approach, associating each effective individual gains.

Figure 1: Intervention training program “Hands on”

3.1 Procedure

SMEs were invited to participate in the program. The criterions used in these selection were regional recognition of good practices in people management and proximity with the university. This paper presents results at an individual level and not aggregated by organization.

The program had as major goals: a) develop creativity and critical thinking skills in the participants; b) promote knowledge about theories of thought and creative behavior, critical thinking theories; c) understand the level of organizational trust experienced in the company; d) Promote hetero-knowledge.

3.2 Participants

To participate in this program 5 SMEs were selected from different sectors: energy, development of new technologies, design and advertising. The sample had a total of 25 participants, 13 females and 12 males. Participants’ age ranged between 20 to 45 years, with an average of 31,74 and a standard deviation of 7,37. Participants time in the company, in average, were 4,42 years with a standard deviation of 4,21.

Table 1: Participants

	Average	SD
Age	31,74	7,37
Seniority	4,42	4,21
Female	13	
Male	12	
Total of participants	25	25

3.3 Instruments

The program had an initial assessment on the first session. Regarding critical thinking, we choose to apply the Critical and Creative Thinking Test (TPCC). It was built and validated for the Portuguese population by José Pinto Lopes, Helena Silva e Eva Morais in 2018. TPCC is for children and adults from 12 years old and can be administered individually or in groups. It consists of presenting a current and everyday problem, where a set of problematic circumstances can be identified. It is intended, after exposing the problem, that the evaluated respond to a set of six questions that require the use of the following skills: a) interpretation – recognize the problem and define it without prejudice; b) analysis - identify the solutions making inferences and compare the solutions showing differences and similarities; c) explanation - defend your position with valid arguments; d) evaluation - recognize the relevant factors to assess the degree of credibility of a source of information or opinion and anticipate questions or objections and assess the weaknesses of the arguments; e) synthesis - improve the solution presented or defined with new arguments and alternatives; and f) production / creation - develop new ideas and solutions in an imaginative and innovative way (Lopes, Silva, Dominguez & Nascimento, 2019). After the application, responses are evaluated using a grid. For each of the six questions, answers are evaluated from 0 to 4, except for 2b and 6b, which are scored from 0 to 3 points (Lopes, Silva, Dominguez & Nascimento, 2019). In this study two different set of problematic from TPCC were applied – one in the first session and other in the last one. Participants initial evaluation of Organizational Trust included specifically organizational level, colleagues/team and management level trust and organizational support. The questionnaire was compiled by Costa (2016). This instrument gathers an adaptation from trust in the Organization, adapted by Robinson and Rosseau (1994), Trust in management, adapted and validated by Adams and Sartori (2006) and Trust in Colleagues, adapted and validated by Adams and Sartori (2006); All items were classified on a seven-point Likert rating scale, which varies between (1) "strongly disagree" and (7) "strongly agree", except for the variable Trust in the Organization, which varies between (1) "strongly disagree" and (5) "strongly agree".

Creativity needs to be assessed as a skill that shows itself in ordinary life, not with standardized test (Sternberg, 2012). Therefore, over the years that have been created batteries of test and prompts to assesses the use of creativity skills in contexts and scenarios (Agnoli, Corazza & Runco, 2016; Sternberg & Coffin, 2012; Torrance, 2018). The Torrance Tests of Creative Thinking - Figural(TTCT-F) embraces five separate norm-referenced assessments of creativity measures, as Fluency, Originality, Elaboration, Abstractness of Titles and Resistance to Premature Closure and criterion-referenced assessments of creativity, as *Storytelling Articulateness, Movement or action, Expressiveness of Titles, Synthesis of Incomplete Figures, Synthesis of Lines, Unusual Visualization, Internal Visualization, Extending or Breaking Boundaries, Humor, Richness of Imagery, Colorfulness of Imagery and Fantasy*. During the intervention, the TTCT was applied two times, with different figures, on the first and the last session. After making these assessments, the scorer looks for evidence of creative strengths, those thirteen, giving ratings of (+) (for 1 or 2 occurrences) or (++) (typically for 3 or more occurrences). The results only refer to criterion-referenced assessments of creativity. This were translated to a 0-2 scale (0 – no occurrence and 2 – 3 or more occurrences) for a better understanding of the results. Synthesis of Incomplete Figures and Synthesis of Lines are not described in the results because those are assessments with TTCT's test that were not applied doing the training course.

3.4 Data Analyses technique

The quantitative analysis of the data was performed in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistical analysis and two-way mixed variance analysis were performed to study differences in the different moments of data collection. Considering the reduced sample size we used non parametric statistic, namely Wilcoxon.

4 Results

This paper presents a pre and post evaluation performed to participants on the training program. Concerning the first TPCC application, presented in the first session, results show low levels of critical and creative thinking among participants. From the six skills evaluated, analysis (M=1,57) and production/creation (M=1,27) revealed the higher levels. In the last session, a second and different version of TPCC was applied. It is possible to see in

table 2 a positive evolution. This time it was analysis (M=2,22), explanation (M=1,49), synthesis (M=1,224) and evaluation (M=1,20), that show the higher levels. Fairly to production/creation skill, it shows a negative evolution (M=1.27; M=0.90). Differences were not statistically significant. Regarding to gender differences in TPCC, they also were not statistically significant. Results show that female participants have higher levels of critical and creative thinking in almost every skill evaluated.

Table 2. Results of TPCC I and TPCC II

	TPCC I		TPCC II	
	X	SD	X	SD
Interpretation	0,704762	0,263932	0,873016	0,357407
Analysis	1,569048	0,260527	2,221005	0,252143
Explanation	1,047619	0,218218	1,493968	0,503014
Evaluation	1,038095	0,313419	1,201624	0,300052
Synthesis	0,7	0,353698	1,224614	0,225225
Production/Creation	1,271429	0,521575	0,902931	0,214335

As we can see from the table 3, from the six skills evaluated, it was analysis (M=1.71; M=2.54), explanation (M=1,5; M=2.15), synthesis (M=0.75; M=2.07) and evaluation (M=1,25; M=1.54) that had higher levels and the most positive evolution. Furthermore, results indicated higher levels of interpretation in the male (M=0.75; M=1) rather than on the female participants (M=0.58; M=0.75). Although the male has lower levels than female participants in the two applications of TPCC, we can also perceive their positive evolution.

Table 3: Gender differences in TPCC

	TPCC I				TPCC II			
	FEMALE		MALE		FEMALE		MALE	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Interpretation	0,58	0,67	0,75	0,80	0,75	0,77	1,00	1,50
Analysis	1,71	0,52	1,50	0,65	2,50	2,54	2,00	1,00
Explanation	1,58	0,80	0,60	0,83	2,15	2,15	1,33	1,12
Evaluation	1,25	0,89	0,93	0,71	1,54	1,54	1,11	0,78
Synthesis	0,75	0,80	0,67	0,62	2,08	2,08	1,22	0,83
Production/Creation	1,41	1,68	1,08	1,16	1,46	1,46	0,89	0,78

Results reveal high levels of Organizational Trust among the participants, namely *Trust in the Leaders* (M = 6, SD= 28.91) and *Organizational Trust* (M = 4.31, SD= 4.67), followed by lower levels related to *Trust in colleagues* (M = 3.5; SD= 64.20). Results related to Creativity, reveal an average increase in the recognition of all the dimensions evaluated, except in the *Internal visualization* dimension. As you can see from graph I, and according to Wilcoxon test, the dimensions with the most positive evolution were *Storytelling Articulateness*, *Richness of imagery*, *Colorfulness of imagery* and *Fantasy*. The *Colorfulness of imagery* revealed a statistically significant positive evolution $z = -2,879, p \leq .005$.

Graph 1 – Creativity Differences Pre and Post

5 Conclusions

This training course was designed for participants already in the work force, but its results show that with efforts focused on critical thinking and creativity these skills can be enhanced and useful for jobs that require a higher education. As Badran (2007) and Ahern, O'Connor, McRuair, McNamar & O'Donnell (2012) put it, critical thinking and creativity should be explicitly addressed in engineering curriculums in order to help students become critical thinkers and consequently, add value to products and services provided by them. On that note, it's important to add the promotion of these skills to the learning objectives of engineering courses. In future researches related to this investigation this goal can be targeted by studying the adaptation and results of this training course with students, more especially engineering students that can benefit and become more prepared to enter on the work force if these set of very appreciated skills are promoted beforehand.

University-business cooperation is crucial on sustainable knowledge exchange and co-creation of knowledge. Regarding SMEs this topic gains even more relevance as academia has been developing relevant projects with organizations but have not being able to diminish the gap towards SME's (Ferreira-Oliveira & Bouças, 2020). This paper presents results from an intervention program, a workshop "hands on" approach with major goals: a) to develop creativity and critical thinking skills in the participants; b) to promote knowledge about theories of thought and creative behavior, critical thinking theories; c) to understand the level of organizational trust experienced in the company; d) to promote hetero-knowledge; e) to develop students proficiency in these skills development. In this paper we present results from the evaluation pre and pos of participants that were under the training sessions. The project had relevant impact in student's professional and personal development; it also showed significant increases in all skills; creativity stands out as the most enhanced skill. The training program was very short, 5 sessions, however regardless, this training had relevant results on participants. Results show relevant differences in skills development, namely on creativity.

University Business Cooperation and Higher education institutions have a very relevant role on establishing bridges with SMEs. Universities should act as talent-engines, developing and validating students' competences but also as a life partner, upskilling professionals (Davey, 2020). In Portugal, the majority of our enterprises are SMEs therefore academia should continue to establish relevant bonds with these organizations that will ensure that they see Higher Education Institutions as major partners through their whole development phase. Future studies should present more extensive programs and an organizational level approach with results from each organization and sector levels of achievement.

6 References

- Aggarwal, Y., & Bhatia, N. (2011). Creativity and innovation in management: a fuel for growth. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(5), 288-296.
- Ahern, A., O'Connor, T., McRuair, G., McNamara, M., & O'Donnell, D. (2012). Critical thinking in the university curriculum – the impact on engineering education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 37(2), 125–132. doi:10.1080/03043797.2012.666516

- Badran, I. (2007). Enhancing creativity and innovation in engineering education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(5), 573–585. doi:10.1080/03043790701433061
- Baptiste, N. R. (2008). Tightening the link between employee wellbeing at work and performance: A new dimension for HRM. *Management Decision*, 46(2), 284–309. doi:10.1108/00251740810854168.
- Brower, H. H., Schoorman, F. D., & Tan, H. H. (2000). A model of relational leadership: The integration of trust and leader-member exchange. *Leadership Quarterly*, 11(2), 227–251.
- Costa, A.C., Roe, R. & Taillieu, T. (2001). Trust within teams: The relation with performance effectiveness. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 10(3) 225-244.
- Cruz, G., Dominguez, C. & Payan-Carreira, R. (2019). A importância e o desafio de educar para o pensamento crítico no séc. XXI. In. *Educar para o pensamento crítico na sala de aula*. Coord. Lopes, J. Silva, H., Dominguez, C., Nascimento, M. Pactor: Edições de Ciências Sociais, Forenses e da Educação.
- Davey, T. (2020). The future of universities. UIIN. 2019 University-Industry Interaction Conference.
- Dirks, K. T., & Ferrin, D. L. (2002). Trust in leadership: meta-analytic findings and implications for research and practice. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(4), 611–628. doi:10.1037//0021-9010.87.4.61.
- Driscoll, J. (1978). Trust and participation in organizational decision making as predictors of satisfaction. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 21 (1) 44-56.
- Ferreira-Oliveira, A. T., & Bouças, A. F. (2020). Retaining Knowledge and Human Resource Management in IT Sector: How We Are SMEs Doing This? *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, 35–44. http://doi:10.1007/978-3-030-45688-7_4
- Ferreira-Oliveira, A. T., Keating, J., & Silva, I. (2018). Decision Making on Human Resource Management Systems. *Trends and Advances in Information Systems and Technologies*, 1040–1045. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-77712-2_99
- Gomes, J. F. D. S., Rodrigues, A. F., & Veloso, A. (2016). Regresso às Origens: A importância do Indivíduo na Criatividade nas Organizações. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea*, 20(5), 568-589.
- Gould-Williams, Julian. (2003). The importance of HR practices and workplace trust in achieving superior performance: A study of public-sector organizations. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 14(1), 28–54. doi:10.1080/09585190210158501
- Guilford, J.P. (1950), "Creativity", *American Psychologist*, Vol. 5/9, pp. 444-454, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/h0063487>.
- Jr, J. L. M., Hansen, M. H., & Pearson, A. W. (2004). The cognitive and affective antecedents of general trust within cooperative organizations. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, 16(1), 48-64.
- Keating, J., Silva, I., & Veloso, A. (2010). Confiança organizacional: teste de um modelo. In A. S. & M. C. T. C. Nogueira, I. Silva, L. Lima, A. T. Almeida, R. Cabecinhas, R. Gomes, C. Machado, A. Maia (Ed.), VII Simpósio Nacional de Investigação em Psicologia (pp. 2451–2466). Braga: Associação Portuguesa de Psicologia.
- Kuvaas, B. (2008). An exploration of how the employee organization relationship affects the linkage between perception of developmental human resource practices and employee outcomes. *Journal of Management Studies*, 45(1) 1-25. doi:10.1111/j.1467-6486.2007.00710.x.
- Lehmann-Willenbrock, N., Grohmann, A., & Kauffeld, S. (2012). Promoting multifoci citizenship behavior: time-lagged effects of procedural justice, trust and commitment. *Applied Psychology*, 62(3), 454–485. doi:10.1111/j.1464-0597.2012.00488.x.
- Levitin, D. (2014). *The Organized Mind: Thinking Straight in the Age of Information Overload*. New York: Penguin Publishing Group USA.
- Lewicki, R. & Bunker, B. (1996). Developing and maintaining trust in work relationships . In Kramer, R. & Tyler, T. (Ed.) *Trust in organizations : frontiers of theory and research* , 114-140. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Lopes, J. P., Silves, H. S., Dominguez, C., & Nascimento, M. M. (2019). *Educar para a sala de aula pensamento: Planificação estratégias e avaliação* (1st ed., Vol. 1). Lisboa: Pactor.
- Lopes, J., Silva, H., & Morais, E. (2019). Teste do Pensamento Crítico e Criativo para estudantes do ensino superior. *Revista Lusófona de Educação*, 44(44).
- Lopes, J., Silva, H., Dominguez, C., Payan-Carreira, R., Catarino, P., Morais, F. e Vasco, P. (2019). O feedback na promoção do pensamento crítico. In. *Educar para o pensamento crítico na sala de aula*. Coord. Lopes, J. Silva, H., Dominguez, C., Nascimento, M. PACTOR: Edições de Ciências Sociais, Forenses e da Educação.
- Lubart, T. (2017). The 7 C's of Creativity. *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 51(4), 293-296.
- Mach, M., Dolan, S., & Tzafrir, S. (2010). The differential effect of team members' trust on team performance: The mediation role of team cohesion. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 83(3), 771–794. doi:10.1348/096317909X473903.
- Mayer, R. C., Davis, J., & Schoorman, F. (1995). An integrative model of organizational trust. *The Academy of Management Review*, 20(3), 709–734.
- Mayer, Roger C; Davis, J. (1999). The effect of the performance appraisal system on trust for management. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 84(1), 123–136.
- Möllering, G., Bachmann, R., & Lee, S. H. (2004). Introduction: Understanding organizational trust - foundations, constellations, and issues of operationalisation. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 19(6), 556-570.
- Perry, R. & Mankin; L. (2007). Organizational trust, trust in the chief executive and work satisfaction. *Public Personnel Management*, 36(2), 165-180.
- Rousseau, D. M., Sitkin, S. B., Burt, R. S., & Camerer, C. (1998). Not so different after all: a cross-discipline view of trust. *Academy of Management Review*, 23(3), 393–404. doi:10.5465/AMR.1998.926617.
- Ruggiero, V. (2014). *Becoming a Critical Thinker*. Scarborough, ON: Nelson Education.
- Ryhammar, L., & Brolin, C. (1999). Creativity research: Historical considerations and main lines of development. *Scandinavian journal of educational research*, 43(3), 259-273.
- Spreitzer, G. M., & Mishra, A. K. (1999). Giving up control without losing control: Trust and its substitutes' effects on managers' involving employees in decision making. *Group & Organization Management*, 24(2), 155-187.
- Sternberg, R. J. (2012). The assessment of creativity: An investment-based approach. *Creativity research journal*, 24(1), 3-12.

- Sternberg, R. J., & Grigorenko, E. L. (2007). *Teaching for successful intelligence: To increase student learning and achievement*. Corwin Press.
- Sternberg, R. J., & Lubart, T. I. (1999). The concept of creativity: Prospects and paradigms. *Handbook of creativity*, 1, 3-15.
- Sternberg, R.J. and T. Lubart (1995), *Defying the Crowd: Simple Solutions to the Most Common Relationship Problems*, The Free Press.
- Torrance, E. P. (1972). Predictive validity of the Torrance tests of creative thinking. *The Journal of creative behavior*, 6(4), 236-262.
- Vincent-Lancrin, S., et al. (2019), *Fostering Students' Creativity and Critical Thinking: What it Means in School*, Educational Research and Innovation, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/62212c37-en>.